

**DEVELOPMENT OF A MAINTENANCE FREE LEAD ACID BATTERY FOR
INERTIAL NAVIGATION SYSTEMS IN LARGE MILITARY AIRCRAFT**

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ABSTRACT

Historically, Aircraft Inertial Navigation System (INS) Batteries have utilized vented nickel-cadmium batteries for emergency DC power. The United States Navy and Air Force developed separate systems during their respective INS Developments. The Navy contracted with Litton Industries to produce the LTN-72 and Air Force contracted with Delco to produce the Carousel IV INS for the large cargo and specialty aircraft applications. Over the years, a total of eight different battery national stock numbers (NSNs) have entered the stock system along with 75 battery spare part NSNs.

The Standard Hardware Acquisition and Reliability Program is working with the Aircraft Battery Group at Naval Surface Warfare Center Crane Division, Naval Air Systems Command (AIR 536), Wright Laboratory, Battelle Memorial Institute, and Concorde Battery Corporation to produce a standard INS battery. This paper discusses the approach taken to determine whether the battery should be replaced and to select the replacement chemistry. The paper also discusses the battery requirements, aircraft that the battery is compatible with, and status of Navy flight evaluation. Projected savings in avoided maintenance in Navy and Air Force INS Systems is projected to be \$14.7 million per year with a manpower reduction of 153 maintenance personnel. The new INS battery is compatible with commercially sold INS systems which represents 66% of the systems sold.

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INTRODUCTION

A wide variety of Navy and Air Force Weapons Systems utilize either the LTN-72 or Delco Carousel IV Inertial Navigation System (INS), both of which require a dedicated battery. Vented nickel-cadmium batteries are currently used for this application, but these batteries suffer from high maintenance costs. In addition, multiple versions of the INS battery exist encompassing eight different National Stock Numbers (NSNs). Some versions contain 15-minute emergency power cells, while other versions contain 30-minute emergency power cells. However, all versions have the same basic footprint and mounting provisions and are compatible with Aeronautical Radio, Inc. (ARINC) Specification 404A short 1/2 ATR case. Tables 1 and 2 present battery identification (part numbers and NSNs) and physical characteristics.

Table 1.
INS Battery Part Numbers

Battery Part No.	INS Type	National Stock No.	Alternate Part Nos.		
			Marathon	SAFT	Eagle-Picher
500012-01	LTN-72	6140-00-253-7855(a)	28002-001		
500012-02	LTN-72	Not assigned	28002-002		
500040-03	LTN-72	6140-01-078-1108 6140-01-074-7150(b)	28885-001		
510014-01	LTN-72	6140-01-302-3815	29448-001		
510018-01	LTN-72	6140-01-300-4773			18085
7883480-011	Carousel IV	6140-00-448-8836(a)	27828-002	19535	
7888701-011	Carousel IV	6140-01-106-1306 6140-01-047-0185(a)	28858-002	19536	

(a) Sourced by Sacramento ALC.
(b) Sourced by DLA.

Table 2.
INS Battery Physical Characteristics

Battery Part No.	INS Type	Capacity, minutes	Max. Weight, lbs	Max. Height, in.	Max. Length ^(a) , in.	Max. Width ^(b) , in.	Venting
600012-01	LTN-72	15	17	6.281	12.62	5.077	Louvered
600012-02	LTN-72	15	17	6.281	12.62	5.077	Forward
600040-03	LTN-72	30	26.5	7.85	12.62	5.077	Forward
510014-01	LTN-72	30	27	7.85	12.62	5.077	Louvered
510018-01	LTN-72	30	26.5	7.85	12.62	5.077	Forward
7863460-011	Carousel IV	15	17	6.312	12.667	5.046	Louvered
7866701-011	Carousel IV	30	27	6.312	12.667	5.046	Louvered

(a) Length does not include handles.
(b) Width includes lid.

DISCUSSION

Program Objective

The objective of this program was to develop a common, 30-minute INS battery utilizing High Reliability, Maintenance-Free Battery technology to reduce INS operation and support costs. The Navy experience with Maintenance Free Battery (MFB) technology on F/A-18 and A/V-8B had demonstrated that significant reliability, maintainability improvements, and cost reductions could be achieved when compared with conventional vented battery technology. Originally, two types of MFB were considered potentially viable for this application. These were sealed lead-acid (SLA) batteries and sealed nickel-cadmium (SNC) batteries. A third type of battery, the ultra low maintenance (ULM) nickel-cadmium battery, was later included as part of the investigation.

Approach

The approach taken to develop a MFB for Inertial Navigation Systems in large military aircraft is described in the following paragraphs.

First, a system analysis was performed. The system analysis included a review of system documentation and actual recording of system data via portable data acquisition during battery operation on the military aircraft. The system analysis looked

at charge and discharge performance and compatibility with the different MFBs.

Next, a life cycle cost study was performed on the existing batteries and compared to expected costs for the new MFB. Data was collected on old systems from Naval Aviation Logistics Data Analysis (NALDA) system and Air Force MODAS system. The reliability data from the Navy and Air Force Reliability and Maintainability Data Analysis System are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3.
NALDA Data For Navy Aircraft

Aircraft	Equipment Flight Hours	Failures	Removals	Total Man-Hours	MTBF (a)	MTBR (b)	Flight Hrs Per Man-Hour	Man-Hours Per Failure
F-5A	1889	-	5	79	-	639	24	-
F-5B	63046	84	272	6463	669	124	10	30
F-6C	814886	246	1878	26143	874	139	8	15
EP-3E	10181	14	82	1339	728	164	8	21
C-130F	7873	3	18	251	8624	695	24	15
KC-130F	87280	23	40	1427	1189	682	19	26
EC-130D	8914	88	87	945	181	128	18	8
KC-130R	6895	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LC-130R	4492	-	1	2	-	4498	2201	2
KC-130T	11007	10	30	582	1101	207	18	19
TOTAL	248445	418	2489	32761	-	-	-	-
AVERAGE	-	-	-	-	854	140	10	14

(a) MTBF = Mean Time Between Failures (Flight Hours ÷ No. Failures).
(b) MTBR = Mean Time Between Removals (Flight Hours ÷ No. Removals).

Table 4.
MODAS Data For USAF Aircraft

Aircraft	Equipment Flight Hours	Failures	Removals	Total Man-Hours	MTBF (a)	MTBR (b)	Flight Hrs Per Man-Hour	Man-Hours Per Failure
C-5A	253848	944	484	8174	375	684	30	10
C-5B	282879	79	275	8780	802	1421	88	7
C-8C	2824	4	4	19	698	698	126	5
KC-10A	286488	80	71	388	4442	8009	1284	4
EC-135	8280	43	8	798	48	242	3	18
KC-135A	12927	1088	289	6820	122	279	13	8
KC-135E	12148	708	88	6270	172	1409	19	9
KC-135Q	27811	138	30	1387	328	1380	27	11
KC-135R	18823	689	180	7787	181	1122	22	8
EC-135C	15443	87	14	1084	166	680	12	13
C-141B	1488278	1841	748	22784	782	1880	82	12
T-43A	27748	80	1	284	488	27748	84	5
TOTAL	202180	6881	2022	65888	-	-	-	-
AVERAGE	-	-	-	-	400	1480	48	10

(a) MTBF = Mean Time Between Failures (Flight Hours ÷ No. Failures).
(b) MTBR = Mean Time Between Removals (Flight Hours ÷ No. Removals).

This data was compared to Navy experience with SLA batteries and information received during solicitation to industry. The life cycle cost analysis looked at cumulative life cycle cost, manpower requirements, and operational capability. Figure 1 presents the cumulative life cycle cost at year 10 while Tables 5 and 6 show manpower and operational capability data from the study.

Figure 1.
Cumulative Life Cycle Cost At Year 10

Table 5.
Manpower Requirements

Battery Type	VNC		SNC	ULM	SLA
	Navy	Air Force	Combined	Combined	Combined
Service Branch	Navy	Air Force	Combined	Combined	Combined
Hours Per Year Flight	416,000	1650000	1963000	1963000	1963000
Man-hours Per Year	65,400	281,700	26,200	29,000	29,000
Man-hours Per 1000 Flight Hours	156.9	170.7	13.4	14.8	14.8
Personnel Equivalents (Men Per Year)	31.3	134.9	12.6	13.9	13.9

Table 6.
Operational Capability Requirements

Battery Type	VNC		SNC	ULM	SLA
	Navy	Air Force	Combined	Combined	Combined
Service Branch	Navy	Air Force	Combined	Combined	Combined
Flight Hours Per Year	416,000	1650000	1963000	1963000	1963000
Unscheduled Removals Per Year	278	733	157	196	196
Scheduled Removals Per Year	3003	18,000	3926	3926	3926
Downtime Hours Per Year ^(a)	2058	10,466	2277	2355	2355
Aircraft Availability	99.508%	99.370%	99.884%	99.880%	99.880%
# Aircraft With INS Battery	550	1900	2450	2450	2450
# Aircraft Available	547	1888	2447	2447	2447

(a) Assumes 0.5 hours downtime per scheduled removal and 2.0 hours downtime per unscheduled removal.

Table 7.
US Navy INS Battery Applications

AIRCRAFT	INS TYPE	BATTERY P/N
P-3A	LTN-72	500012-01
P-3B	LTN-72	500012-01
P-3C	LTN-72	500012-01
EP-3E	LTN-72	500012-01
C-130F	LTN-72	500012-01
KC-130F	LTN-72	500012-01
EC-130Q	LTN-72	500012-01
KC-130R	LTN-72	500012-01
LC-130R	LTN-72	500012-01
KC-130T	LTN-72	500012-01
PINS	LTN-72	500012-01

One important aspect in life cycle cost was the standardization/economy of scale gained by establishing a standard INS battery. Tables 7 and 8 show the applicable weapon systems and number of systems in the military inventory.

The third step was to select a battery and write a selection report. The battery selection was made based on compatibility of the battery with existing charging methods (different in each system design), amount of system modification, system reliability, and total life cycle costs. The battery chemistry/design selected during the battery selection step was the SLA battery. Table 9 presents the selection matrix that was developed during the selection process. The SLA battery pick represented the lowest risk for development and represented the shortest payback period of 8 months.

Next, a specification was developed using parameters from existing documentation, from

instrumentation of the INS, and military aircraft battery specifications. The specification developed was a specification sheet to MIL-B-8565J. This specification sheet is now designated as MIL-B-8565/13-1.

Table 8.
US Air Force INS Battery Applications

AIRCRAFT	INS TYPE	BATTERY P/N	AIRCRAFT	INS TYPE	BATTERY P/N
C-5A	C-IV	7888701-011	C-135E	C-IV	7888701-011
C-5B	C-IV	7888701-011	EC-135A	C-IV	7888701-011
C-9A	LTN-92	500040-03	EC-135C	C-IV	7888701-011
C-9C	LTN-92	500040-03	EC-135E	C-IV	7888701-011
KC-10A	LTN-72	500012-01	EC-135G	C-IV	7888701-011
C-18A	C-IV	7888701-011	EC-135H	C-IV	7888701-011
C-18B	C-IV	7888701-011	EC-135J	C-IV	7888701-011
EC-18B	C-IV	7888701-011	EC-135K	C-IV	7888701-011
EC-18D	C-IV	7888701-011	EC-135L	C-IV	7888701-011
C-22A	C-IV	7888701-011	EC-135N	C-IV	7888701-011
C-22B	C-IV	7888701-011	EC-135P	C-IV	7888701-011
VC-25A	LTN-92	?	EC-135Y	C-IV	7888701-011
C-27A	LTN-92	?	KC-135A	C-IV	7888701-011
C-130E	C-IV	7888701-011	KC-135E	C-IV	7888701-011
C-130H	C-IV	7888701-011	KC-135Q	C-IV	7888701-011
EC-130E	C-IV	7888701-011	KC-135R	C-IV	7888701-011
EC-130H	C-IV	7888701-011	NC-135A	C-IV	7888701-011
HC-130H	C-IV	7888701-011	WC-135B	C-IV	7888701-011
HC-130N	C-IV	7888701-011	NKC-135A	C-IV	7888701-011
HC-130P	C-IV	7888701-011	NKC-135E	C-IV	7888701-011
LC-130H	C-IV	7888701-011	C-137B	LTN-72	?
NC-130H	C-IV	7888701-011	C-137C	LTN-72	?
WC-130E	C-IV	7888701-011	C-141B	C-IV	7888701-011
WC-130H	C-IV	7888701-011	NC-141A	C-IV	7888701-011
C-135A	C-IV	7888701-011	E-3B	C-IV	7888701-011
C-135B	C-IV	7888701-011	E-3C	C-IV	7888701-011
C-135C	C-IV	7888701-011	E-4B	C-IV	7888701-011

Table 9.
Selection Matrix

Criteria	SNC	ULM	SLA
Performance/Environmental Compatibility	Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Satisfactory
Acquisition Cost (\$M)	8.9	5.1	4.0
LCC at Year 10 (\$M)	55.4	48.6	46.0
Technology Risk	Moderate	Moderate	Low
"Qualified" Sources	2	1	2
Overall Rating (a)	C	B	A

(a) A is the highest rating; C is the lowest rating.

Existing electrical and environmental information from existing company documentation used to establish the MIL-B-8565/13-1 requirements are shown in Tables 10 and 11, respectively.

Figure 2.
New MFB (left) and Vented INS Batteries

Table 10.
INS Battery Electrical Requirements

Parameter	Litton Specifications		Delco Specifications	
	16-Minute Battery	30-Minute Battery	15-Minute Battery	30-Minute Battery
Nominal Voltage	24 volts DC	24 volts DC	24 volts DC	24 volts DC
Nominal Capacity	6.5 AH @ C15 rate	15 AH @ C15 rate	6.5 AH @ C15 rate	15 AH @ C15 rate
Circuit Breaker	30 Amperes	30 Amperes	30 Amperes	30 Amperes
Power Output	375 W (continuous)	375 W (continuous)	400 W (continuous) 425 W (peak)	400 W (continuous) 425 W (peak)
* Minimum Duration**	15 minutes (40-122 F)	30 minutes (40-122 F)	15 min. @ 400W (41-180 F) 1 min. @ 425 W (6-180 F) 21.0 volts	30 min. @ 400 W (41-180 F) 1 min. @ 425 W (6-180 F) 21.0 volts
* Minimum Voltage	18.0 volts	18.0 volts		

* Minimum duration is undefined outside of indicated temperature range.

Table 11.
INS Battery Environmental Requirements

Parameter	Litton Specification (E00040)	Delco Specification (ST 7800436)
Surrounding Temperature		
Storage	-65 to 165 F	-65 to 160 F
Operational	-40 to 140 F	0 to 160 F
Full Performance	+40 to 122 F	+41 to 160 F
Humidity	95% RH max. Test per RTCA DO-138, Category B	95% RH max. Test per MIL-E-5272, Procedure 1
Altitude		
Normal Operation	< 22,300 ft.	1,000 to 25,000 ft.
Emergency Operation	< 43,300 ft.	100 to 45,100 ft.
Decompression	8,200 to 40,000 ft. in 10 min.	9 psi drop to 45,100 ft. in 15 sec.
Vibration	RTCA DO-138, Category K&O	MIL-E-5272C, Procedure XII
Shock	10 G max. for 12 milliseconds Test per RTCA DO-138, Section 8.0	15 G max. for 11 milliseconds Test per MIL-E-5272C, Procedure V

Using this specification sheet, a procurement package was developed to procure a 10 ampere-hour SLA battery. A development contract was awarded to Concorde Battery Corporation to qualify the

battery. Qualification testing was completed on the battery during FY94. Batteries are presently under flight evaluation at Naval Air Station (NAS); Brunswick, Maine to test cold temperature performance and NAS Jacksonville, Florida to test hot temperature performance.

Also during FY94, action was taken to stop the procurement of existing cells, batteries, and battery parts. During FY95 the initial procurement for Fleet introduction will be performed by the Defense Logistics Agency. The battery will enter the Fleet by attrition instead of the recommended on-time change out due to present Navy operation and maintenance budget shortfalls. Aircraft manuals and Navy battery maintenance manuals will also be updated.

Applicability of the Battery

The battery is applicable to 3850 military systems presented in Tables 7 and 8. Litton later produced the LTN-92 Laser Ring Gyro INS system which used the same configuration battery. Besides the 3850 military systems that use the battery there are over 10,000 similar INS systems that were sold to Commercial Airline Companies. These batteries are compatible with these commercial INS systems.

CONCLUSION

The Maintenance Free Inertial Navigation System Battery development has been successfully completed. The development has resulted in a Standard INS Battery that is compatible with the LTN-72, LTN-92, and Carousel IV INS systems.

The benefits from the application of the Standard INS Battery in military aircraft will reduce the number of battery NSNs in the supply system from 8 to 1, eliminate 75 spare parts NSNs from the supply system, improve aircraft availability by 12 aircraft, result in a manpower reduction of 153 personnel per year (figured into the avoided

maintenance savings), and avoided maintenance savings of 14.7 million per year. One important conclusion that should be restated is that it is compatible with commercial aircraft systems which could obtain the same operating benefits.

All Questions and Comments Should Be Directed To:

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